

ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF TEACHING PHYSICAL CULTURE AT SCHOOL

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Abstract. *This article gives a general description of the organization of the role of physical culture in shaping the personality of students, their interests and creative abilities, in improving motor and psychophysiological qualities, in promoting health and preventing diseases of schoolchildren in the structure of general secondary education, the subject should be of an applied nature, occupy one of the leading places in the system of interdisciplinary connections and contribute to the solution of important general pedagogical decisions.*

Keywords: *dynamics, health, physical culture, complex, pedagogical, biomedical, psychological.*

In the last decade in modern society, the main idea is to preserve the health of the younger generation, as a fundamental factor in the future well-being of the state.

An analysis of the state of health of the children's population indicates an increase in the incidence of children. Such dynamics of the state of health is the result of a long-term impact of adverse socio-economic and environmental factors.

In a general education school, physical culture is the basic area of education. This is confirmed by the analysis of the curricula of domestic and foreign schools, where physical culture occupies one of the priority places.

This position of this area of culture is due to the fact that it lays the foundations of physical and spiritual health, on the basis of which only and truly diverse development is possible. personality. This shows the value of physical culture for the individual and society, its educational, educational and general cultural significance.

The most important element of physical culture is motor culture, which includes the main ways of moving in space, overcoming obstacles, performing motor actions with objects. No less important is the totality of means developed in society to promote the development of motor abilities and the education of the individual as a whole.

The teaching of physical culture at school is organically included in the general system of education and upbringing and operates according to the laws of education and upbringing. At the same time, this is the only academic subject that forms in students a competent attitude towards themselves, towards their body, contributes to the education of new volitional and moral qualities, the need for strengthening health and self-improvement.

In accordance with the socio-economic needs of society and based on the essence of general and secondary education, it is clear that the goal of the subject "Physical Education" is to contribute to the formation diversified personality. The means of achieving this goal for the teacher is the mastery of the basics of physical culture by schoolchildren. In general, this means a set of needs, motives, knowledge, an optimal level of health and development of motor abilities, normal physical development, the ability to exercise motor, physical culture and health and sports activities.

When conducting physical education lessons, I rely on modern psychological-pedagogical and physiological-pedagogical theories of education, upbringing and personality development, using active methods of education and upbringing, taking into account personal wasps the particularities of each child. The principles of activity and personal approaches are that the student masters the ways of using the wealth accumulated by mankind in the field of bodily and spiritual perfection.

Democratization and humanization of the educational process are possible on the basis of the idea of a joint developing activity of children and adults, in the process of which they are connected by mutual understanding and penetration into the spiritual world of each other, with a joint desire to achieve high results in training and education.

The upbringing of a culture of health, a healthy lifestyle, teaching students the techniques of mobilization and relaxation, bodily and spiritual self-improvement led to the need to revise the existing content of the physical education in educational institutions. In the light of the foregoing, the subject "Physical culture" in a general education school is understood as the unity of two components - orienting children and adolescents in the field of physical culture and creative activity.

The first component is designed to create in children a holistic view of physical culture and health culture as elements of a common culture.

The second component directs the process of physical education to the creative assimilation of the methods of self-active, as well as the ability to apply them in solving health-improving, educational and educational tasks.

Changes in the system of general secondary education lead to the development of a new concept of physical education. For this, it is necessary, in addition to a complex of pedagogical, biomedical, psychological and sociological studies in the field of physical culture, to clearly define and legitimize the role and place of physical culture in the educational process , its relationship and interaction with other academic disciplines, while maintaining the integrity of the learning process, while in which each item contributes to the harmonious development of the child's personality.

At present, an extensive increase in the amount of material studied in all disciplines continues, its oversaturation with new, not always necessary, knowledge. This leads to a break in interdisciplinary connections: each subject solves its own problems on its own, and students experience passivity and indifference to everything related to learning.

Thus, a new concept of physical education is impossible without an objective analysis and critical rethinking of the processes taking place in education as a whole.

It is difficult for students to remember everything that is given to them in the lessons. The compilers of scientific concepts and curricula often "forget" about the psychophysiological capabilities of children in receiving and processing information, about the age and sex characteristics of their development, and natural social needs. Intensive training loads on a fragile children's organism adversely affect the health of schoolchildren. The lack of motor activity and excessive training loads often lead to a breakdown in basic biological functions. All this indicates that the education system in its current form has become a powerful pathogenic factor in various diseases of schoolchildren that disrupt the normal course of important psychophysiological processes (thinking, mental work capacity, attention, memory). Naturally, this state of affairs

should worry those who are entrusted with the health of children, on whom the preparation of school graduates for adult life depends.

It is obvious that physical education is an effective means of solving many problems.

However, as practice confirms, for 3 lessons of physical education per week they cannot solve all problems enough. Moreover, as a result of scientific and technological progress, the motor activity of children has sharply decreased. Now the guys have a special respect for television and computer games. The negative consequences of this are on the face, because the growth, development and health of a person directly depends on his motor activity. Popular wisdom says: "Movement is health!"

At present, in the system of physical education, there are three main directions of the modern lesson in the subject "Physical culture" - recreational, training and educational.

Not so long ago, the training direction of the lesson was considered the leader. Practically no due attention was paid to the lessons of health and educational orientation. The purpose of these lessons is for the child to acquire such special knowledge that he will be able to transfer into everyday life and usefully apply in other activities. Such a lesson should solve the following tasks:

In elementary school - the formation of general ideas about physical culture, its significance in human life; development of mental processes of creativity, independence, consciousness, tolerance; teaching elementary ways of self-control over physical development and physical fitness.

In the basic and secondary schools - deepening the basics of knowledge about physical culture; education of positive individual mental traits and characteristics in communication and collective interaction, tolerance; creation of ideas about individual psychosomatic and psychosocial characteristics, adaptive properties of the body and ways to improve them in order to improve health; development of self-control skills, responsibility for one's health; studying the cultural and historical foundations of physical culture.

The system of educational lessons based on work experience gives a number of positive results, developing mental processes (thinking, memory, attention, self-control skills), having an educational impact in the formation of healthy schoolchildren's way of life.

The activities of teachers are aimed both at achieving the optimal level of education, upbringing of students, and at providing conditions for the preservation and development of health. The most significant components in physical education are:

- determination of loads in physical education classes and their differentiation, taking into account the physical development and health of children;
- implementation of generally accepted sanitary and hygienic measures (ventilation, wet cleaning, compliance with thermal and light conditions);
- introduction to the educational plan of health lessons, preventive conversations, the introduction of physical education minutes during the lessons;
- improvement of the system of physical culture and sports events;
- systematic conduct of educational activities on a healthy lifestyle, personal hygiene;
- regular medical examination of students on the basis of the district clinic;
- monitoring of physical fitness and health level.

Of course, each educational institution independently draws up the structure of health blocks, depending on the material and technical capabilities, goals and objectives of student health programs.

The school has a sports hall with shower rooms and equipped locker rooms. The school has a stadium with artificial turf. All this allows to increase the effectiveness of the lessons and increases the interest of students in physical education and sports. The school has sections "Table tennis", "volleyball", "Football"

A very relevant question is how to form a desire to engage in physical education in school-age children? The answer, in my opinion, includes four elements.

The first is a description of the goal to be achieved.

The second is action motivation. It is necessary to rely on a motive significant for the student.

The third is the practical implementation of the leading motive.

The fourth is the result that should be achieved after completing the training work.

In the same way, you can form a positive attitude and interest in the performance of almost any activity by a student.

Experts say that today the guarantee of victory in the sports arena is not only a high level of technical skill of an athlete, but also the creation of an artistic image by him.

Integrations are possible with mathematics, biology, and physics. Options can play a significant role in developing the humane personality traits of students.

Music is the key building block. Depending on the selected music, an image is created and the child's motor potential is realized.

Music determines the nature of movement, its development, creates an emotional basis for action, thereby contributing to the implementation of health-saving technologies.

Improvisation can be an effective means. For improvisation, children can be offered exercises that convey the movements of animals, images of plants, and labor activity.

For the development of children's speech, it is desirable to supplement exercises with rhymed texts or recitative in physical education lessons.

Dance movements, of course, can have a very strong impact on a person, on his psychophysical recovery. In addition to individual dance movements, dance-expressive training can be used in lesson forms.

It is impossible to ignore the influence of color on our life, on our health. Positive emotions are manifested when the eye is sensitive to the red-yellow part of the spectrum, and negative to blue-green colors. Knowledge of the effect of color on the human body can be used by choosing a color when painting a hall, choosing a sports uniform, sports equipment. So, yellow is considered a brain stimulant, it does not tire and has a stimulating effect on vision and the nervous system, purple color has a calming effect, reduces anxiety, green raises vitality, relieves stress, irritability.

A complex combination of the means of music, fine arts, dance in the system of physical education of schoolchildren can be used in theatrical mass performances, in sports holidays, and at every lesson in story-ro left games.

Thus, the main rule for using the forms and methods of art in physical education is not to be afraid to improvise, combining the motor component (physical culture) with the spiritual (art), to show creativity and imagination, to teach this to children, because it is so necessary in modern life.

The pedagogical experience of using musical-rhythmic outdoor games shows that in addition to physical ones, children develop aesthetic and moral qualities, mental and musical

abilities, as well as speech, logical and imaginative thinking. The fusion of music and physical culture, complementing each other, contributes to the improvement of the educational process.

The role of the family (parents) in maintaining the health of children and their physical development is very great. To begin with, it is necessary to determine the main thing: communicate more with your own children, engage in physical education with them as often as possible - play fun and games, compete, push to records, and thereby save protect children from diseases, stress, malnutrition, smoking and alcohol.

Performing various physical exercises, you need to know that the child makes everyone smile, but not everyone - to think. The problems of the future of any family, and the future of the country, directly depend on the main thing - who will build. Both family and country. People are free, beautiful and strong or insecure, sickly, illiterate and characterless. It depends largely on the parents, on how carefully, carefully, meaningfully and inventively they reveal the possibilities and talents of their children. It is necessary to go in for sports together with children, be interested in their success, set a positive example.

All upbringing and all education is strung on one rod - diligence. Everything else - curiosity, attention, memory, abilities - everyone has, though in different proportions. And from this it follows that with a child who is difficult to remember, it is necessary to work differently.

Those who do not succeed in all ways must be tried to support, to cultivate self-respect. Such a system of work would help solve many children's problems. And family problems - also related to children and their free time.

To correct the situation with the "sick generation", the effective work of school specialists in physical education is necessary, and the competent actions of the parents of schoolchildren should become the necessary support in their activities.

In my opinion, it is necessary to start from the basics: to develop normative requirements for the development of motor qualities for children entering grade I; to acquaint the parents of future first-graders with regulatory requirements; conduct testing of future students upon admission to the school; organize seminars and consultations for parents on the development of the motor qualities of children. Fully functioning television, propaganda, and the press should also make their contribution.

The lessons of physical culture from the 1st to the 11th grade should be taught by specialists; after all, it is in the primary school that the basic physical education knowledge, skills and abilities are laid, most importantly, the motivation for further physical self-improvement.

It is well known that regular physical exercise gives many-sided positive effects, the physiological basis of which is used in medicine for the treatment, rehabilitation and prevention of various diseases.

Optimal motor activity, as it were, turns on the mechanisms of recovery and keeps them in working condition, which increases the body's resistance to various pathogenic factors and contributes to a quick recovery in case of illness. The lack of movements creates conditions for the manifestation of a hereditary predisposition to diseases and, therefore, limits the suitability for certain professions, darkens the prospect of future motherhood and fatherhood.

The organism seeks to maintain an individual norm of motor activity, which allows us to speak of an innate need for it.

Why did the problem of children's health come to the fore? Yes, only because it continues to deteriorate, and "Physical Education" is the only subject in the school that can effectively solve

the problem of the health of students – it is stubbornly relegated to “secondary roles”. It is gratifying to note that at present the Government of our country pays great attention to the development of physical culture and sports. This is confirmed by the introduction of the third hour of physical education into the curriculum, the construction of unique sports centers, and the holding of mass sports competitions of various levels.

What can be done to optimize the health-improving, developing and educational components within the new, multifaceted role of physical culture?

The implementation of the health-improving component requires the development of specific requirements for the level of health of schoolchildren, as a unity of physical and intellectual factors. All this allows us to state that the role of physical culture is extremely important in shaping the personality of students, their interests and creative abilities, in improving motor and psychophysiological qualities, in strengthening health and preventing tics of diseases of schoolchildren. Therefore, in the structure of general secondary education, the subject should be of an applied nature, occupy one of the leading places in the system of intersubject communications and contribute to the solution of important general pedagogical tasks.

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